

ORIGINAL VERSION OF THE SCRIPT

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armoval. At the table in the middle of the room find SARGE, cataloguing evidence bags. Various TECHS crisscross the room now and then, searching for delivering evidence.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

For the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. Not only do I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a childminder? Well, don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

As long as you're here, make yourself useful and hit that light switch. It's a bit dark in here.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change to a calming blue, and soothing, meditative music begins to play.

SARGE (CONT'D)

What the hell...? Turn it off, turn it off.

User One complies.

SARGE (CONT'D)

It's all controlled by computer or something... we haven't been able to gain access. Rich people, eh? Always finding new ways to throw their money away.

Turning to User Two.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well, how about you put new batteries in that torch there.

Next to User Two is a table with a flashlight, battery compartment open, and a large battery. User Two can pick up the battery with one hand and the light with the other, and

insert the battery into the compartment. Screwing the cap on turns on the beam.

SARGE (CONT'D)

There now. That's better.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking device.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, Rachel, there you are.

(turning to the Users)

This is our Technology Officer, Rachel Long. She's going to set up this new AI system that's got everyone in a frenzy. Rachel... the Civilian Oversight Committee I was telling you about.

RACHEL

Yes... hello.

She nervously lays the device on the table and begins setting it up.

SARGE

Seems like a lot of nonsense, but they say since she was such a public figure, there's enough data to make it work. If you ask me, it's good old-fashioned detective work that will solve this case.

Rachel finishes her final adjustments and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other. Sarge flashes his badge.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been robbed? I have a very sophisticated security system. You control it

with that remote you have there...
along with everything else in the
apartment.

Sarge slides the remote across the table toward User Three.

SARGE

Oh good, maybe the light switch is
on there.

ELENA

Just hold down button three for a
few seconds, that will reset
everything in the room to the
default settings.

User Three does so, and the lights come up to normal.

SARGE

Ten million Euros to tell us how to
turn the lights on. That's quite
the investment.

Rachel stiffens, eager to show off what the technology can
really do.

RACHEL

Miss Armova, we were wondering what
you could tell us about last night.
Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and
more
agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why
can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do
remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting
with my board of directors... I was
supposed to meet Christine later...
Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant.
I should call her, she'll be
worried...

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it. Any idea where you might have left it?

ELENA

I usually set it on the charger when I come home... just over there by the entrance.

The charger is clearly empty.

ELENA (CONT'D)

But I have a phone finder in that drawer there.

She points to a table behind User 4.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make the phone alarm. It's a separate unit from the phone, so it works even if the phone's off.

User 4 opens the drawer, removes the remote and presses the button. One of the evidence bags on the table begins to make a really annoying noise. Sarge picks up the bag, and we see a small round button shaped device inside. Sarge presses it, and the noise stops.

SARGE

So that's what that is. Found it in the trash earlier. Seems someone doesn't want us to find your phone, Miss Armova. Can you think of any reason why that might be?

ELENA

No... I don't know...

SARGE

Do you believe that either Miss Gerard or your boyfriend, Mr. Zeller, would have any reason to wish you harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I was planning on ending things with Ryan. I do expect him to be quite upset when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the
temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA
No... if you must know. I was
involved with someone else.
Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE
Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA
None of your business, Officer.

SARGE
A crime's been committed here,
"Miss Armova". I'll need to
interview this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel,
annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Can't you do something?

RACHEL
Like what?

SARGE
Make her answer.

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Look, Miss... whatever you are.
We're trying to solve a murder
here.

ELENA
A murder? Whose?

SARGE
Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions--

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA
Mine? That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE
No, a hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing here

talking to me, and I don't have time for the coy games. Tell me who the other fella was, or I'm turning you off.

RACHEL
Actually... the procedure for shutting her down--

SARGE
It. The thing is a machine, Rachel.

RACHEL
Right, but it's a very complex machine, so...
Rachel's voice trails off as she notices that Elena's hologram has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker here as she gets further away from the projection device?). She quickly picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...
She follows Elena into an adjoining room. Sarge turns to the group, specifically to address User 5.

SARGE
Well well... how about you. Do you think we'll get an answer out of her about her new beau? Yes or no?
--option 1--

USER 5
Yes.

SARGE
Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 5
No.

SARGE
Me neither. Waste of time, most likely.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Either way, I'm headed into the kitchen to do some real police work. Follow me or go with Rachel and her little toy, up to you.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women. The

Users decide which group to follow.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is examining two wine glasses by the sink.

SARGE

Two different shades you say?
That's interesting. What are the chances she changed lipsticks in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS who have decided to join him.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, good. Now you'll get to see some real crime-solving. Evans here was just telling me that there are two different shades of lipstick on these wine glasses. Having a drink with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three different sets of fingerprints, actually.

SARGE

Three? Now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, then pulls out the card and puts it on the table.

EVANS

If you could stick that in my laptop there and hit enter, the the program is all set up. It'll do the rest.

User 1 goes to the table and inserts the card, presses Enter. The computer screen flashes to an image that says "processing" and some kind of progress bar.

SARGE

Let me guess... Armova, Gerard and Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2: Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Sometimes it doesn't take a rocket scientist. So which sample came from which glass?

Evans turns the laptop and starts pecking at keys.

EVANS
Interesting thing... One glass had all three fingerprints. The other, just Gerard.

SARGE
So either one of them could have put something in her drink.
(thinks a moment, turns to the Users)
Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in my assumptions back there with that... device?
(to User 2)
Tell me, yes or no: do you think Armova's new love interest... was Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2
Yes.

SARGE
Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2
No.

SARGE
You sure? Something Zeller said when we brought him in... about pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Fair to say there were enough secrets among the three of 'em to fill a teenage girl's diary.

RACHEL (O.S.)
Sarge? Evans? We found something!

Sarge and Evans look at each other, curious.

SARGE

Let's have a look then.
Sarge leads the group out.

Evans picks up his laptop and tags
along behind.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL)-

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users enter to find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed,
staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her,
Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

Rachel looks up from the device.

RACHEL

Ah, good. I've got her settled down
a bit. I think she'll be more
responsive now.

(turning to Armova)

Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who
the new person in your life was...
is? We'd really like to talk to
them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

At least you didn't assume, like
that old dinosaur in there.

Her eyes wander back to the picture.

ARMOVA (CONT'D)

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are
arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at
first. What Zeller couldn't get out
of me with pillow talk, he paid
Gerard to supply. But his plan
backfired. Christine and I fell in
love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did you ever suspect she was doublecrossing you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA
No! Christine would never betray me like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL
Do you think she suspects more than she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1
Yes.

RACHEL
Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1
No.

RACHEL
Something about her body language tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Miss Armova... what were you celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA
A major deal with a Greek resort chain. Christine had only been working for me for a few months. She was still on Ryan's payroll, but the sparks were flying. Late nights, traveling together... our first kiss was a few weeks after this picture was taken. But...

She becomes emotional.

RACHEL
What is it, Miss Armova? You can tell us. It's very important that

you're completely honest with us.

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA

Everything you need to know is on the SD card hidden in that picture frame.

Rachel looks to User 2, nodding toward the picture frame-

RACHEL

Go ahead... see what you can find.

User 2 picks up the picture frame, pulls the back off, and finds an SD card taped to the back of the picture.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Sergeant Hoffstetler will want to see that right away.

Rachel and the Users head back toward the Living Room.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

Rachel's group enters the space first, following Rachel.

RACHEL

Sarge? Evans? We found something! She turns to the User who has the picture frame.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Go ahead and set that on the table.

The other group enters, led by Sarge. Rachel indicates the frame now lying on the table.

Sarge pulls the SD card off the frame and hands it to Evans, who sits down and puts it into his laptop.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

(to Sarge)

Did you find anything interesting in the kitchen?

SARGE

You bet. Fingerprints on the wine glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both had the opportunity to introduce the poison into Armova's glass. Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL

Gerard... so that could be motive.

EVANS
And so could this.

All attention in the room focuses on Evans as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)
Seems Armova had someone hack into Gerard's bank accounts... she was receiving payments from Zeller every few weeks... up until just last Monday.

RACHEL
She never stopped working for Zeller. If Armova found out... Gerard might have good reason for wanting to keep her quiet.

SARGE
Sounds like we have motive, means and opportunity, ladies and gentlemen. Time to bring in Miss Gerard... in handcuffs this time.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy piece of technology is worth something after all.
(to the Users)
And thanks for your help. You're welcome back any time, as far as I'm concerned. Good work, everyone. Someone hit that light switch again, eh?

He stretches out on the sofa and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)
I think I've earned a bit of a kip.

A User hits the switch on the wall, and the lights fade down to the dim blue they were before, and then all the way to black.

THE END

ADAPTED SCRIPT DUE TO COVID-19

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armova. At a table in the middle of the room find SARGE.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Just for the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a nanny? Don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

While you're here, make yourself useful, it's a bit dark in here. Hit that light switch, would you?

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, turn it on.

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, on the wall, behind you, turn on the lights!

(When they do:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

There we go, that's better.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking device.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, Rachel.

(turning to the Users) Everybody, This is Rachel Tyrell, she's our Tech Officer. Rachel, this is the Civilian Oversight Committee I was telling you about. Rachel is going to install the AI system that's got everyone in a frenzy.

RACHEL

Yes... hello.

SARGE

Seems like a lot of nonsense, but they say since she was such a public figure, there's enough data to make it work.

Rachel lays the device down on the table, looks at it and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been robbed? I have a very sophisticated security system.

Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and more agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting with my board of directors... I was supposed to meet Christine later... Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant. I should call her, she'll be worried..

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it. Any idea where you might have left

it?

ELENA

I have a phone finder.

She points to a table behind User Four.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make the phone ring.

SARGE

Go on, then.

Presumably User Four presses the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Go on, press the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Press the button on the remote that's on the cabinet, go on!

(Once they do:) One of the evidence bags on the table begins to make a really annoying noise.

SARGE

So that's what that is.

SARGE

Look, Ms. Armova, do you have any reasons to suspect why Christine Gerard or your boyfriend, Ryan Zeller, may wish you to do harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I was planning on ending things with Ryan. I do expect him to be quite upset when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA

No... if you must know. I was involved with someone else.

Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE

Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA

None of your business, Officer.

SARGE
Look, "Miss", I'm trying to solve
a crime here. I need to get to know
this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel,
annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Can't you do anything with her?

RACHEL
Like what?

SARGE
Like make her answer!

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Look, Miss... whatever you are.
We're trying to solve a murder
here.

ELENA
A murder? Whose?

SARGE
Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions—

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA
That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE
No, you're not. A hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing right here
talking to me, and I don't have time
for the coy games. So if you don't tell me who
the other boyfriend is, I'll turn you
off!

Rachel notices that Elena's hologram
has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker here as she
gets further away from the projection device?). She quickly
picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...

She picks up her machine and follows Elena into an adjoining
room. Sarge turns to the group, addressing User Five.

SARGE
Well well... you, listen out.
Do you think we'll
get more information about her
new beau out of her?

--option 1--

USER 1
Yes.

SARGE
Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 1
No.

SARGE
Me neither. Waste of time, if
you ask me.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Either way, I'm headed into the
kitchen to do some real police
work. Two groups, two of you
with me, and two of you with Rachel
and her new toy.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is
examining three glasses by the sink.

SARGE
Two shades?
That's interesting. What are the
chances Armova changed her lipstick
in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Ah, there you are. Now you'll get to
see some real police work.
Young Evans here was just telling me that
there are two different shades of lipstick on the
glasses. So what, Armova was having a drink
with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the
glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three

different sets of fingerprints,
actually.

SARGE
Three? Uh, now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, and the information
appears.

SARGE
Don't tell me... Armova, Gerard and
Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2:
Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)
You see, sometimes you don't have
to be a rocket scientist.
So which sample came
from which glass?

EVANS
Gerard, Zeller and Armova.

The results pop up.

SARGE
So either one of them had a
good opportunity to put
some poison in her drink.
(thinks a moment, turns to
the Users)
Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in
my assumptions back there with
that... device?
(to User 2)
Tell me, yes or no: do you think
Armova's new love interest... was
Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2
Yes.

SARGE
Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2

No.

SARGE

You sure? Something Zeller said when we brought him in... about pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)

Fair to say there were enough secrets between the three of 'em to fill a teenage girl's diary.

(beat)

But it's not enough to get a conviction, not yet. I do hope Rachel's group has something. You two stay, I'm gonna see what she found.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL)-

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed, staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her, Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

RACHEL

Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who the new person in your life was... is? We'd really like to talk to them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at first. What Zeller couldn't get out of me with pillow talk, he paid Gerard to supply. But his plan backfired. Christine and I fell in love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did you ever suspect she was doublecrossing you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA
No! Christine would never betray me like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL
Do you think she suspects more than she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1
Yes.

RACHEL
Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1
No.

RACHEL
Something about her body language tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Miss Armova... what were you celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA
A major deal with a Greek resort chain. Christine had only been working for me for a few months. She was still on Ryan's payroll, but the sparks were flying. Late nights, traveling together... our first kiss was a few weeks after this picture was taken. But...

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA
Everything you need to know is on the SD card hidden in that picture frame.

Rachel looks to User Two, nodding toward the picture frame. Rachel takes it.

Rachel picks up the back of the picture frame (the part that has the SD card taped to it) and heads for the door.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
I'll see if Sarge has finished in
the kitchen. Wait here for a moment.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

The groups arrive in the Living Room together to find Sarge, Rachel waiting for them.

RACHEL
Sarge, we found something here, and you?

She pulls the SD card into his laptop.

SARGE
You bet. Fingerprints on the
glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both
had the opportunity to put poison her.
Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL
Gerard... so that could be motive.

All attention in the room focuses on Sarge as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)
Seems Armoval had someone hack into
Gerard's bank accounts... she was
receiving payments from Zeller every
few weeks... right up until last
Monday.

RACHEL
She never stopped working for
Zeller. If Armoval found out...
Gerard she had a good reason
to keep her quiet.

SARGE
Looks like we have, means, motive
and opportunity, ladies and
gentlemen. I think it's time to bring in
Miss Gerard, once again.
This time, in handcuffs.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy

toy of yours is worth
something after all.

(to the Users)
And thanks to all of you. You're
welcome back any time, as far as I'm
concerned. Good job, everyone.

He stretches out and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)
I think I've earned a bit of a rest.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Go on then, don't make me change
my mind back again.

(Assuming they do:) A User hits the switch on the wall, and
the lights fade down to the dim blue they were before, and
then all the way to black.

THE END